

Course for Doctoral Students

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT AND OPEN DATA

25th July 2015, Social Science Data Archives,
Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana

ECPR Summer School 2015

ACCESS TO SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA: RESEARCH, ELECTION RESULTS, OFFICIAL STATISTICS

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Social Science Data Archives

Content

- Popular portals for Social Scientists
- CESSDA
- European Social Survey
- European Election Database
- Atlas of European Values
- [Official Statistics microdata](#)
 - DWB project and training courses
 - *metadata systems CIMES and MISSY*
 - *Access to EU official statistics microdata and aggregate data*
 - *Access to census microdata*
 - *Access to official statistics microdata in Slovenia /SI-STAT data portal*

International data

Basic registration required

[ZACAT](#), [DBK](#), [DATORIUM](#)

CESSDA

Variable and question bank

CESSDA - A new pan-European Research Infrastructure

CESSDA provides large scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. CESSDA will support national and international research and cooperation in areas expected to be of great importance in the future.

CESSDA is organised as a limited company under

DATA CATALOGUE

The data Catalogue provides a seamless interface to datasets from social science data archives across Europe. It is available in nine languages.

[Go to the Data Catalogue](#)

NATIONAL DATA SERVICES

Find your National Data Service

NEWS

Fri 10 Jul 2015

[Ensuring a healthy future for scientific research through the Data Protection Regulation](#)

Position of academic, patient and non-commercial research organisations – June 2015.

Mon 1 Jun 2015

EVENTS

Mon 27 Jul 2015 - Fri 31 Jul 2015

[ICPSR 5-day workshop July 2015](#)

This workshop is for individuals interested or actively engaged in the curation and management of research data for sharing and reuse, particularly data librarians, data archivists, and data producers and stewards with responsibilities for data

Search

 English

Help on Searching Data | Contact

CESSDA Catalogue

Browse by Topic

Browse by Keyword

EDUCATIONAL PLANNING AND ADMINIS

ELECTRIC POWER GENERATION

ELECTRIC POWER STATIONS

EMOTIONAL STATES

ENERGY

ENVIRONMENT

ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES

ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

EQUIPMENT

ESOTERIC PRACTICES

ETHICS

EVALUATION

EXAMINATIONS

EXPECTATION

EXPERIENCE

EXPLOITATION

FACILITIES

FAILURE

FAMILIES

EXTENDED FAMILY

ONE-PARENT FAMILIES

FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

Browse by Data Publisher

Search Term: **EXTENDED FAMILY**

Study Section Variable

Variable	Study	Archive
No. Extended Family	HBS 2004	ISSDA
No. Extended Family	HBS 1987	ISSDA
No. Extended Family	HBS 1994	ISSDA
No. Extended Family	HBS 1999	ISSDA
Familie/utvidet familie	Clinical social workers in child and adolescent mental health care. Professional development and clinical praxis, 2007	NSD
Familie/utvidet familie	Clinical social workers in child and adolescent mental health care. Professional development and clinical praxis, 2007	NSD
No.of Nuclear Families	HBS 1987	ISSDA
No.of Non Family Members	HBS 1987	ISSDA
No.of Relatives	HBS 1987	ISSDA
No.of Nuclear Families	HBS 1994	ISSDA

1- 10 of 547 | Next >

Assigned Keyword Search

Related Terms:

- FAMILY ENVIRONMENT (25576 hits)
- FAMILY LIFE (6436 hits)
- FAMILY MEMBERS (96144 hits)
- FAMILY SIZE (802 hits)
- TRIBES (17 hits)

National Data Services

CESSDA Members

- [Austria](#)
- [Czech Republic](#)
- [Denmark](#)
- [Finland](#)
- [France](#)
- [Germany](#)
- [Greece](#)
- [Lithuania](#)
- [Netherlands](#)
- [Norway](#)
- [Slovenia](#)
- [Sweden](#)
- [Switzerland](#)
- [United Kingdom](#)

Rotating modules for ESS Round 8 announced

The ESS ERIC Scientific Advisory Board has selected the two successful modules for ESS Round 8. More...

29 Countries

The 3rd International ESS Conference • 13-15th July 2016 • Lausanne, Switzerland [MORE >>](#)

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

ESS Resources

The ESS provides a series of outreach resources designed to increase the use of its data, including ESS Bibliography, Findings, Training Courses and eLearning resources.

About ESS

About ESS
Contact Information
Project Specification
Structure and Governance
Funding
News
Participating Countries
National Pages
User Statistics
Conference 2016

Methodology

ESS Methods Overview
Sampling
Translation
Questionnaire
Pre-Testing and Piloting
Improving Question Quality
Response and Non-Response
Mixed Mode Data Collection
Measuring National C
Attitudinal Indicators

Data and Documentation

Data and Documentation by Year
Data and Documentation by Country
Data and Documentation by Theme
Online Analysis
ESS Data Alerts
Conditions of Use
Fieldwork Summary and Deviations
Cumulative Data (Wizard)

Resources

ESS Bibliography
ESS EduNet (eLearning)
ESS Findings
ESS Training Courses
ESS on Wellbeing

About ESS Methodology Data and Documentation Resources

Home » Bibliography » Bibliography

ESS Bibliography

The ESS Bibliography contains information about public national European Social Survey. This includes analysis methodology research and descriptions and documenta

[ADVANCED SEARCH](#) | [SEARCH TIPS](#)

The complete bibliography referenced in compliance with the Harvard System

<< first < prev **1** 2 3 4 5 6 7 next > last >>

Search results: 158 hits (click on column headers to sort)

Title	Author(s)	Year	Type	Published in/by
Educational inequality as an example of unsustainable use of human resources	Beilmann, Mai Roots, Ave Sammul, Marek	2015	Conference paper/poster	
Neo-Nationalism in Western Europe	Eger, Maureen A. Valdez, Sarah	2015	Journal article	European Sociological Review
Prevention of social exclusion of elderly people and support for active and dignified ageing	Õun, Kandela Rähn, Anne	2014	Book chapter	Sustainable Welfare in a Regional Context
Who have the right to live as a family in Estonia?	Kurs, Eveliis Ainsaar, Mare	2014	Newspaper/magazine article	Eesti Ekspress
Is there class society in Estonia? Who are the rich, who are the poor	Päärt, Villu	2014	Newspaper/magazine article	Õhtuleht
Patterns of Family Life Courses in Europe – between Standardisation and Diversity: A Cross-national Comparison of Family Trajectories and Life Course Norms in European Countries	Hofäcker, Dirk Chaloupková, J.	2014	Journal article	Comparative Population Studies
Modelling the relationships between work-to-family conflict, work and family stressors and well-being	Fedáková, Denisa Dobeš, Marek	2014	Journal article	Člověk a společnost - Individual and Society
Work-family conflict in Sweden and Germany: A study on the association with self-rated health and the role of gender attitudes and family policy	Tunlid, Sara	2014	Thesis, dissertation	
Does gender matter? Policies, norms and the gender gap in work-to-home and home-to-work conflict across Europe	Fahlén, Susanne	2014	Journal article	Community, Work and Family
Töö- ja pereelu tasakaalustamine Eesti infotehnoloogiaettevõtetes	Taba, Nele	2013	Thesis, dissertation	
Is Old Age Stigma?	Rapoliéné, Gražina	2013	Conference paper/poster	
Comparison of Perception Safety in Relation to Selected Work Attributes in the Countries of the European Social Survey	Bozogáňová, Miroslava Tomková, Jana	2013	Conference paper/poster	
Chances and Challenges of demographic change	Blinkert, Baldo	2013	Book	LIT Verlag Münster
Capabilities and Childbearing Intentions in Europe: The association between reconciliation policies, economic uncertainties and women's fertility	Fahlén, Susanne	2013	Journal article	European Societies

- ESS
 - ESS1-2002, ed.6.4
 - ESS2-2004, ed.3.4
 - ESS3-2006, ed.3.5
 - ESS4-2008, ed.4.3
 - ESS5-2010, ed.3.2
 - ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

- Metadata
 - Study Description
- Variable Description
 - Country
 - Weights
 - Media and social trust
 - Politics
 - Subjective well-being, social exclusion, religion, national and ethnic identity
 - Personal and social well-being
 - Gender, Year of birth and Household grid
 - Socio-demographics
 - Human values
 - Administrative variables
 - Understanding of democracy
 - User defined variables

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Abstract

The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically-driven multi-country survey, which has been administered in over 30 countries to date. Its three aims are, firstly – to monitor and interpret changing public attitudes and values within Europe and to investigate how they interact with Europe's changing institutions, secondly - to advance and consolidate improved methods of cross-national survey measurement in Europe and beyond, and thirdly - to develop a series of European social indicators, including attitudinal indicators.

In the sixth round, the survey covers 29 countries and employs the most rigorous methodologies. It is funded via the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme, the European Science Foundation and national funding bodies in each country.

The survey involves strict random probability sampling, a minimum target response rate of 70% and rigorous translation protocols. The hour-long face-to-face interview includes questions on a variety of core topics repeated from previous rounds of the survey and also two modules developed for Round Six covering Europeans' Understandings and Evaluations of Democracy and Personal and Social Wellbeing (the latter is a partial repeat of a module from round 3).

Full Title

ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Alternative Title

ESS6-2012

Identification Number

ESS6e02.1

Bibliographic Citation

European Social Survey (2014). ESS Round 6 (2012/2013) Technical Report. London: Centre for Comparative Social Surveys, City University London

Martin: Centre for Comparative Social Surveys (CCSS), City University London, UK. Geert Loosveldt, Jaak Billiet and Hideko Matsuo: Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium. Bjørn Henrichsen, Knut Kalgraff Skjåk, and Kirstine Kolsrud: Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD), Norway. Angelika Scheuer, Sabine Häder, Achim Koch, Matthias Ganninger, Verena Halbherr, Brita Dorer and Stefan Zins: GESIS, Germany. Willem Saris, Wiebke Weber, Diana Zavala Rojas and Bruno Arpino: Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain. Ineke Stoop, Joost Kappelhof and Henk Fernee: The Netherlands Institute for Social Research (SCP), Netherlands. Brina Malnar: University of Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Let's start with a simple exercise comparing **life satisfaction measures** of two groups – the **unemployed people looking for work** versus **people in paid work**. Calculate the **means** for the two groups across Europe.

Variable mnactic: Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded

LITERAL QUESTION

F17c2. POST CODE: I

Values	Categories	Code	Frequency	% of all	% of valid
	Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded				
1	Paid work	1	25,760	47.1	47.6
2	Education	2	4,704	8.6	8.7
3	Unemployed, looking for job	3	2,978	5.4	5.5
4	Unemployed, not looking for job	4	1,155	2.1	2.1
5	Permanently sick or disabled	5	1,291	2.4	2.4
6	Retired	6	12,819	23.4	23.7
7	Community or military service	7	90	0.2	0.2
8	Housework, looking after children, others	8	4,796	8.8	8.9
9	Other	9	520	1.0	1.0
66	Not applicable				
77	Refusal	77	39	0.1	-
88	Don't know	88	105	0.2	-
99	No answer	99	416	0.8	-
	Total		54,673	100.0	100.0

SUMMARY STATISTICS

This variable is numerical

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Socio-demographics

- Doing last 7 days: no answer
- Interviewer code, one/more than one doing last 7 days
- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post code
- Interviewer code, respondent in p...
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent...
- Employment contract unlimited or limited duration
- Establishment size

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

Choose 'Add to column' to place the variable here.

To populate this table you need to select a variable from the browse list, click on it and then add it to row, column or layers, or use it as a measure variable.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national g...
- How satisfied with the way demo...
- State of education in country now
- State of health services in countr...
- Government should reduce differences in income levels
- Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

	Median	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Sum	Count
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded							
Paid work	7.5	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.2	179,423.0	25,653
Education	8.0	7.7	0.0	10.0	1.9	35,885.0	4,676
Unemployed, looking for job	5.6	5.4	0.0	10.0	2.7	16,028.0	2,956
Unemployed, not looking for job	5.7	5.6	0.0				
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5	0.0				
Retired	7.0	6.5	0.0				
Community or military service	7.6	6.9	0.0				
Housework, looking after children, others	7.2	6.6	0.0				
Other	7.6	7.0	0.0				
Total	7.30	6.76	0.00				

Change selection ✕

Search for categories

All
 Paid work
 Education
 Unemployed, looking for job
 Unemployed, not looking for job
 Permanently sick or disabled
 Retired
 Community or military service
 Housework, looking after children, others
 Other

Main activity, la...dents. Post coded

All
 Categories
 Change selection...
 Move to column
 Use as Filter
 Remove from table
 Insert calculation

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Satisfaction with life vs. employment

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Next, let's confirm the [correlation](#) between providing help and life satisfaction. Is it [significant](#)? Make sure you check variables response codes to be sure – for ex. do high numbers mean satisfaction or do they mean low satisfaction? Use the variables **'(B20) How satisfied with life as a whole'** and **'(D37) Provide help and support to people you are close to'**.

LITERAL QUESTION

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?
extremely satisfied.

Values	Categories
0	Extremely dissatisfied
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	Extremely satisfied
77	Refusal
88	Don't know
99	No answer

D37. And to what extent do you provide help and support to

Values	Categories
0	Not at all
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	Completely
7	Refusal

DESCRIPTION	TABULATION	ANALYSIS
CORRELATION	REGRESSION	

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Listwise Correlation analysis: [\[Change to pairwise\]](#)

Variables:
No variables added

Choose variables from the browse list.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole Add to correlation.
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national government
- How satisfied with the way democracy works in country

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Listwise Correlation analysis: [\[Change to pairwise\]](#)

Variables:

- How satisfied with life as a whole [\[Remove\]](#)
- Receive help and support from people you are close to [\[Remove\]](#)

	How satisfied with life as a whole	
Receive help and support from people you are close to	0.272 **	** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05

Personal and social well-being

- Receive help and support from people you are close to
- Provide help and support to people you are close to
- Your place in society Add to correlation.
- Physically active for 20 minutes or longer last 7 days

B25. Still using this card, please say what you think overall about the state of health services in [country] nowadays?

- | Values | Categories |
|--------|----------------|
| 0 | Extremely bad |
| 1 | 1 |
| 2 | 2 |
| 3 | 3 |
| 4 | 4 |
| 5 | 5 |
| 6 | 6 |
| 7 | 7 |
| 8 | 8 |
| 9 | 9 |
| 10 | Extremely good |
| 77 | Refusal |
| 88 | Don't know |
| 99 | No answer |

Variables:

- How satisfied with life as a whole [\[Remove\]](#)
- State of health services in country nowadays [\[Remove\]](#)

	How satisfied with life as a whole	
State of health services in country nowadays	0.373 **	** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Country: Categories ▾

Measure: State of health s...nowadays, average ▾

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Use help!!

Front Page

GETTING STARTED

- Nesstar Webview
- Using Webview
- Exploring Data
- Creating Tables
- Manipulate Tables
- Analysis
- Graphics

SEARCH

- Simple Search
- Advanced Search
- Search Results

METADATA

- Description
- Metadata

TOOLS

- Insert Calculation
- Subset by Cases
- Weighting
- Compute and Recode
- Recode
- Bookmarks

DOWNLOAD

- Download Data & Documentation
- Subset Data
- Save Output

Compute and Recode

The 'Compute' option provides pre-defined mathematical and statistical operations on a subset of existing variables into new variables.

Note: For the Σ icon to be visible, you must use the Configuration tool. refer to [webview help](#).

To use the 'Compute' option:

1. Select the compute icon Σ if the variable you want to use has no data.

The system will retrieve any variables you have previously generated or have access to.

2. If there are no previously generated variables a 'Create' box will appear containing a list of calculation types and the 'Recode' option.

Compute

Create

Please select a type of calculation Σ

Please select a type of calculation

- Add
- Subtract
- Multiply
- Divide
- Percent
- Average
- Percent growth
- Recode

3. Using the 'Create' box select a predefined formula, or 'Recode' to begin to compute a new variable.
4. If user defined variables already exist these can be deleted from the 'Delete' menu.

Download

Please select a data format from the drop-down box. If you wish to download a subset of the data, click on the 'Subset' button. Click on 'Download' to start downloading. Please note that you may be asked for a password.

-- Select Data Format -- Σ DOWNLOAD SUBSET

Include computed variables

Include documentation

SPSS, STATA, SAS, R

Download the documentation

Please select a download format from the drop-down box. Click on 'Download' to start downloading.

In pdf format Σ DOWNLOAD

FINDING DATA

ADVANCED SEARCH

Advanced Search - Mozilla Firefox

zocat.gesis.org/webview/velocity?mode=searchview&searchtype=advanced&&

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Variable contains health

Search for: datasets variables

Study Description

- Study Description
- Bibliographic Citation
- Title Statement
- Full Title
- Identification Number
- Responsibility Statement
- Authoring Entity
- Production Statement
- Producer
- Copyright
- Funding Agency/Sponsor
- Distributor Statement
- Data Distributor
- Abbreviation
- Depositor
- Study Scope
- Subject Information
- List of Keywords
- Topic Classification
- Abstract

SEARCH

ZA4768: EVS 2008: Lithuania
[ZA4768 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Variable v9: describe your state of health these days (Q4)

LITERAL QUESTION
Q4
<SHOW CARD 4>
All in all, how would you describe your state of health these days? Would you say it is

- 5 other missing
- 4 question not asked
- 3 nap
- 2 na
- 1 dk
- 1 very good
- 2 good
- 3 fair
- 4 poor
- 5 very poor

Atlas of European Values

Percentage of people that have a great deal or quite a lot of confidence in the health care system

Data by country

Austria
Belgium
Bulgaria
Croatia
Cyprus
Czech Republic
Denmark
Estonia
Finland
France
Germany
Greece
Hungary
Iceland
Ireland
Italy
Latvia
Liechtenstein
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Macedonia
Malta
Montenegro
Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Romania
Slovakia
Slovenia

that incorporate additional statistical measures as demography, labour market, etc.

Data are collected from national election authorities, national statistical agencies and other official sources.

Click on the labels to explore the data.

Slovenia

HEAD OF STATE: President Dr Borut Pahor

HEAD OF GOVERNMENT: Prime Minister Janez Janša

NATIONAL ASSEMBLY (*DRŽAVNI ZBOR*): 90 members

LAST ELECTION: Presidential, 11 November and 2 December 2012

NEXT ELECTION: Legislative, due 2015

Parliamentary Elections

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Presidential Elections

Election results 2012. Electoral

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Candidate		PAHOR	TÜRK	ZVER
Round	Region			
1	SLOVENIA	39.87	35.88	24.25
	Kranj	37.43	33.95	28.62
	Postojna	46.21	34.28	19.50
	Ljubljana Center	35.34	41.79	22.88
	Ljubljana Bezigrad	37.67	39.00	23.32
2	Celje	43.78	32.81	23.41
	Novo Mesto	40.20	36.02	23.78
	Maribor	41.79	36.17	22.03
	Ptuj	38.03	32.23	29.74
	Other	19.02	28.31	52.66
	SLOVENIA	67.37	32.63	-
	Kranj	69.00	31.00	-
	Postojna	70.03	29.97	-
Ljubljana Center	58.85	41.15	-	
Ljubljana Bezigrad	62.94	37.06	-	
Celje	71.79	28.21	-	
Novo Mesto	69.18	30.82	-	
Maribor	66.75	33.25	-	
Ptuj	72.39	27.61	-	
Other	65.46	34.54	-	

Presidential Elections

Election results 2012. Electoral Districts

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Candidate		PAHOR	TÜRK	ZVER	
Round	Region				
1	SLOVENIA	39.87	35.88	24.25	
	Kranj	37.43	33.95	28.62	
	Postojna	46.21	34.28	19.50	
	Ljubljana Center	35.34	41.79	22.88	
	Ljubljana Bezigrad	37.67	39.00	23.32	
	Celje	43.78	32.81	23.41	
	Novo Mesto	40.20	36.02	23.78	
	Maribor	41.79	36.17	22.03	
	Ptuj	38.03	32.23	29.74	
	Other	19.02	28.31	52.66	
	2	SLOVENIA	67.37	32.63	-
		Kranj	69.00	31.00	-
		Postojna	70.03	29.97	-
Ljubljana Center		58.85	41.15	-	
Ljubljana Bezigrad		62.94	37.06	-	
Celje		71.79	28.21	-	
Novo Mesto		69.18	30.82	-	
Maribor		66.75	33.25	-	
Ptuj		72.39	27.61	-	
Other		65.46	34.54	-	

46.21 34.28 19.50
35.34 41.79 22.88

Elections 1990–2015

Year	Parl	Pres	EP	Ref
1989				
1990				
1991				
1992	q	q		
1993				
1994				
1995				
1996	q			
1997		q		
1998				
1999				
2000	q			
2001				
2002		q		
2003				q
2004	q		q	
2005				
2006				
2007		q		
2008	q			
2009			q	
2010				
2011	q			
2012		q		
2013				
2014				

About DwB project

- European Commission supported 4-year project 2011-2015
- Supporting equal and easy access to official statistics (OS) microdata for the European research area
- Bridging three communities (national statistics institutes, (social science) data archives/services, scientific researchers and research institutes)
- Servicing researchers with official statistics metadata
- Developing standards, microdata access procedures, regulation and legislation, also for transnational access
- Promoting using OS microdata for research purposes (organizing workshops, staff visits, conferences)

Training for microdata users

- DwB organized 6 training courses for microdata users in 6 different countries
- Target group: microdata users such as scientific researchers or PhD students
- Structure of training courses:
 - Theoretical part, about microdata access to European OS microdata
 - Hands on sessions, working with carefully prepared, integrated and harmonized Eurostat microdata
 - Focus on either Adult Education Survey, EU Labour Force Survey, EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions or Integrated European Census Microdata
- Similar training organized by GESIS in Mannheim, Germany

CIMES - Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

- information system providing an overview of European official microdata disseminated for research purposes
- structured metadata for national official statistics microdata
- 3 levels of metadata: series, study and dataset
- 31 European countries, 248 series, 1570 studies, 1821 datasets documented

The screenshot displays the CIMES (Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics) web application. The top header shows the CIMES logo and the tagline 'Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics'. A user is logged in as 'Reader DWB'. The main content area is divided into two panels. The left panel, titled 'Series and studies for SLOVENIA', lists various statistical series with their respective country flags. The 'Census - 2011' series is highlighted in orange. The right panel provides detailed information for the selected 'Census - 2011' study. It includes the original title 'Popis - 2011', the original alternative title 'Registrski popis - 2011', the English alternative title 'Register-based Census - 2011', and the producer 'SORS'. An abstract follows, describing the register-based census as a regular statistical survey conducted by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, based on Regulation (EC) No. 763/2008. It notes that the methods of data collection are left to EU Member States, and Slovenia adopted the Medium-Term Programme of Statistical Surveys 2008-2012. The abstract also mentions that the method of data collection used in the register-based census where SORS links existing statistical and administrative data collections is also used in most of the statistical surveys. Acquisition and integration of data is allowed by Articles 32 and 33 of the National Statistics Act (Official Journal of the RS, No. 45/95 and 9/2001; consolidated text). All administrative sources from which we take over the data have the legal basis for the primary collection in the laws governing a particular source. The results of this integration and data processing are aggregated data and the identification of individuals is not possible. With the transition to the register-based census, Slovenia joins few European countries that have already implemented this way of collecting and processing data on population, households and dwellings (Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, Iceland) or will do so for the first time in 2011 (Austria, Belgium, Sweden, Norway). By doing this, Slovenia has not only reduced the administrative burden but also saved EUR 14 million.

MISSY - Microdata Information System for Official Statistics

- online service platform providing structured metadata for official statistics, including Eurostat microdata
- covering Adult Education Survey, EU Labour Force Survey, EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions, Community Innovation Survey, Structure of Earnings Survey

- 5 levels of metadata:

series, study, country study, dataset and variable levels

- distribution channel for „setup files“ - software program codes for import and basic processing of EU microdata

gis Contact | Help

missy. Metadata for Official Statistics

Missy-Home General Information **Find Metadata** Work with myMetadata ?

[Home / Find Metadata / CIS](#)

Variables in myMetadata Box 0

via Series

AES **CIS** EU-LFS EU-SILC

SES

Browse Series

Select Study of CIS

2008 2006 4 3

Materials

via Matrix

via Topic

Series: CIS

Titles

Title Community Innovation Survey

Abstract

The Community Innovation Survey (CIS) is a survey of innovation activity in enterprises. The harmonized survey is designed to provide information on the innovativeness of sectors by type of enterprises, on the different types of innovation and on various aspects of the development of an innovation, such as the objectives, the sources of information, the public funding or the expenditures. The CIS provides statistics broken down by countries, type of innovators, economic activities and size classes. The survey is currently carried out every two years across the European Union, some EFTA countries and EU candidate countries. In order to ensure comparability across countries, Eurostat, in close cooperation with the countries, has developed a standard core questionnaire starting with the CIS3 data collection, along with an accompanying set of definitions and methodological recommendations. The concepts and underlying methodology of the CIS are also based on the Oslo Manual — second edition of 1997 and third edition of 2005.

DFG

DwB

Mitglied der
Leibniz
Leibniz-Gemeinschaft

- Data Version
- Keywords
- Processing
- Data Access
- Data Service
- Comparability
- Notes
- References

Access to European official statistics microdata

- Eurostat harmonizes and merges microdata for official statistics research of national statistical offices
- Eurostat also distributes the microdata for scientific use
- microdata are available for researchers of organizations, which are recognized as a research entity
- LFS, CIS, SES, EU-SILC, AES, CVTS (Continuing Vocational Training Survey), CSIS (Community Statistics on information Society), ERFT (European Road Freight Transport Survey), MMD (Micro-Moments Dataset) datasets
- two modes of access to microdata:
 - on electronic devices (CD/DVD) - anonymized versions
 - in the safe centre in Luxembourg - non-anonymized versions

Access to Eurostat official statistics aggregated data

- publically available data in the form of tables
- users can create their own tables by managing the display (countries, statistics, variables etc.)

The screenshot displays the Eurostat website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Eurostat logo, the text "Your key to European statistics", and links for "Sign In", "Register", "Legal notice", "RSS", "Cookies", "Links", "Contact", and a language selector set to "English". A search bar is also present with the placeholder text "Type a keyword, a code, a title...". Below the navigation bar, a breadcrumb trail reads "European Commission > Eurostat > Data > Database". The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column, under the "DATA" tab, lists various options: "DATABASE", "Information", "Browse statistics by theme", "Statistics A - Z", "Population Census 2011", "Bulk download", "SDMX Web Services", "Access to microdata", "GISCO: Geographical Information and maps", "Metadata", "Classifications", "Legislation and methodology", "Concepts and definitions", "Glossaries and thesauri", "National methodologies", "Standard code lists", and "Euro-SDMX Metadata Structure (ESMS)". The right column, under the "DATABASE" tab, shows a "Data Navigation Tree" with two main sections: "Database by themes" and "Tables by themes". Both sections list the same categories: "General and regional statistics", "Economy and finance", "Population and social conditions", "Industry, trade and services", "Agriculture, forestry and fisheries", "International trade", "Transport", "Environment and energy", and "Science and technology".

Access to census microdata

- Access to detailed microdata (ScUF): Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia distributes Slovenian Census microdata (2002, 2011, 2015 coming soon)
- Access to moderately protected microdata (SUF): IECM/IPUMS Europe distributes European census data (19 countries, 55 censuses and totaling more than 90 million person records) - emphasis on harmonization
- Access to anonymized microdata (PUF): Slovenian Social Science Data Archives distribute Slovenian Census microdata (2002, 2011) - limited number of variables, less detailed data (aggregated variable values)

Access to official statistics microdata in Slovenia

- access to microdata for research and analysis enabled by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia
- available to Slovenian and international researchers (researchers in the general government sector, registered research institutions, registered researchers, also students working with registered researchers)
- three modes of access: safe room, remote access, DVDs
- theoretically, all microdata listed in the Annual Programmes of Statistical Surveys could be available
- requests are handled by the Data Protection Committee; a contract should be signed if access approved

SI-STAT data portal

- data in the form of tables, provided by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia
- one-stop access to statistical data from different fields of statistics and different sources

REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA
STATISTICAL OFFICE RS

SI-STAT Data Portal » Demography and social statistics » List of tables » Data selection / Variables and values

Basic population groups by sex, Slovenia, quarterly

Information Footnotes Statistical Signs

Data selection / Variables and values

Edit and calculate Save As

Basic population groups by POPULATION GROUPS, SEX and QUARTER		2013Q1	2014Q1	2015Q1
Population - TOTAL	Men	1019061	1020874	1022229
	Women	1039760	1040211	1040645
Citizens of the Republic of Slovenia	Men	956940	955927	954877
	Women	1010496	1008550	1006465
Foreign citizens	Men	62121	64947	67352
	Women	29264	31661	34180

Footnote:
Sources: Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, Ministry of the Interior - Central Population Register, Ministry of the Interior - Administrative Internal Affairs Directorate.

Collaboration of the Slovenian Social Science Data Archives and the Statistical Office

- both organizations were partners of the DwB project
- collaboration in the national level, consolidating partners' expert knowledge and experience
- preparing metadata for the most important official statistics microdata
- preparing microdata (e.g. LFS, register data, Census microdata) for immediate statistical analyses with the selected statistical software package promoting microdata use for research purposes
- organizing workshops for students to promote microdata use for study purposes (distributing Public Use Files)

Overview

- recognizing research potential in official statistics data
- increasing support for microdata access in the European area (also for transnational access and remote access)
- establishing national collaborations to improve microdata access services
- various publically available aggregated data sources
- improving metadata systems and availability of metadata to support release of microdata
- increasing need for distribution of Public Use Files - publically available protected microdata

Questions?

LEARNING HOW TO ARCHIVE DATA